

Supporting Information for "Impact of Tidal Forcing on Surface Particle Transport Properties: Insights from Twin Ocean Simulations"

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Figure S1. Backward FTLE fields [$days^{-1}$] on day 01 of each month for the non-tidal simulation.

Figure S2. Backward FTLE [days^{-1}] on day 01 of each month for the tidal simulation.

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